

BEGINNER CLASS MATHEMATICS IN LESSONS LOGIC OF STUDENTS METHODS OF FORMING THINKING

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Abstract. This article describes ways until development logical thinking skills in elementary school student in Math classes.

Keywords: thinking thinking processes analysis synthesis logical problem numerical connection, mathematical puzzles, logical puzzle.

Spatial imagination, mathematical thinking is goal-oriented and goal-oriented, independent search and finding of ways of actions to solve practical tasks, these all together mathematics successful acquisitions for Demand will be done. Child school stepping on the threshold, he does not lose his interest in the game, he is as before there will be revenge for the game. Even interesting issues arouse activity and thinking in children develops.

In order to form the mathematical thinking of elementary school students interesting math games, puzzles, geometric problems and exercises, challenging Arithmetic problems, funny problems, riddles with mathematical content as a tool is appropriate to use. Mathematical games enrich the knowledge of students and their mental activity helps to grow. Mathematical games, other terms have their own characteristics being to think of the students in them forced circumstances their interesting helps students to develop their intellectual and creative abilities. An interesting mathematician games are a tool that has a comprehensive impact on the development of students' thinking considered his using mental and voluntary development done is increased.

We encountered such situations in elementary math classes. This in classes to the students numbers about issues, mathematician sophisms, puzzles, matter, poem, a joke issues solve recommendation will be done. Of these some of them we bring:

a) Numbers about issues.

Get three different numbers in a row and get two possible ones room numbers collection make up Harvest has been numbers sum is given numbers in total be You have the answer 22 will be For example: 3, 4, 5

we get numbers. Let's make a set of possible two-digit numbers: 34, 35, 43, 45, 53, 54.

$$34+35+43+45+53+54 = 22$$

$$3+4+5$$

b) Beloved number

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one of the students your favorite number is offered .

SHE IS wanted ie 6 the number said let it be

- well his how feature have – that interested remains student. It's amazing knowing if you say good saw your number 9 to multiply and came out number (54) is the following 123456789 Multiplier under numbers by doing write.

×12345678

54

666666666

c) A puzzle.

How old is a girl (hours). they asked. His the answer was thought provoking. "Three from next I am three years old from the bar threeyear previous of our age three the bar subtract she is without you have my my age harvest will be", that answer gave

Solution: We denote the sought number by x, then its age after 3 years x+3 to and 3 year first age x-3 will be As a result the following to Eq havewe will be:

$$3(x+3)-3(x-3)=x$$

$$3x+9-3x+9=x$$

$$X=18$$

So, she is 18 year old it is.

Har how mathematician games some kind of mathematician to theory is based on They are of students abstract concepts in learning in training of children thinking developing activity increases. Because them oral The speed of calculation is the sense of competition sharpness, the most to the goal right road with reach desire obvious to the eye thrown away stands In mathematics game to science has been interest increases, this while always serious to engage in need gives birth Pascal the word with so to speak mathematics so serious because him little interesting to do opportunity from the hand not to give must

Below are more mathematical puzzles that develop logical thinking we bring:

$$1 + 4 = 5$$

$$2 + 5 = 12$$

$$3 + 6 = 21$$

$$8 + 11 = ?$$

4	+		+	2	15
+		+		+	
	+	5	+	7	15
+		+		+	
8	+	1	+		15
15		15		15	

3	+		=	9
-		-		-
2	+		=	5
=		=		=
1		3	=	4

Math puzzle

$$\begin{array}{|c|c|c|} \hline \# & = & 9 \\ \hline + & = & 1 \\ \hline \# & = & ? \\ \hline \end{array}$$

A puzzle 3 to the group one at the time is given. Which group fast and right if he does will be the winner.

Through these given examples and puzzles, students' logical thinking is developed.

General purpose of summative lessons in elementary mathematics course - it is to repeat the main concepts of the mathematics course, deepen them while waxing them, systematize the students' knowledge of this subject, and form the students' mathematical logical thinking through examples and problems.

In conclusion, we can say that the above-mentioned materials are close to children with their interestingness and structure. Puzzles, geometrical mathematical problems put students in such conditions that they are forced to think. The positive feelings created in the students during the lesson are one of the main

conditions for the formation of mental abilities. A positive result of systematic work aimed at forming the mathematical thinking of elementary school students leads to the formation of logical thinking.

We recommend this article to primary school teachers and graduate students of higher education.

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